

Livelihood Conditions of the Inhabitants of the Fringe Villages of Pilibhit Tiger Reserve

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The "livelihood approach" has produced the most thorough information regarding the many livelihood methods used by households. The "livelihood approach" proponents believe that "livelihood activities" are more than just a collection of tasks people perform to meet their basic needs; rather, they are the outcome of the interaction between different skills, assets (such as social and material resources), and tasks necessary for a living. It means that, livelihood activities are the result of people using capital for supporting their livelihood activities. Department For International Development (DFID) (1999) have identified five capitals and assets (human, natural, financial, physical and social) based on which people draw their livelihoods. Livelihoods are made up of a series of decisions about how these assets are used. Based on these decisions, members of the family will carry out a series of livelihood activities: cultivating a crop, catching fish in a lake, raising cattle, gathering forest products, or working for another person, etc. Pilibhit tiger reserve is home to a variety of wild animals. People living in the neighboring villages are always worried about being attacked by tigers. In the past, the villagers were not too afraid about the presence of tigers in the reserve. However, according to them "now that the reserve has been approved, the man-eating tiger is present in the reserve". Also, the rapid increase in tiger attacks has also put them in trouble. They are no longer allowed to enter the forest land for honey, fruit or even firewood. The forest area has been banned for them to enter permanently.

Livelihoods are the means by which households obtain and maintain access to the resources (physical, natural, financial, human and social) necessary to ensure their immediate and long-term survival, increase their capabilities and assets to withstand stresses and shocks and to manage risks that threaten their well-being (Anon., 2000b). The sustainable livelihoods facilitate more employment and income opportunities, increased well-being, reduced poverty and vulnerability, enhanced adaptation and resilience, food and nutrition security, improved health, education and social services based upon sustainable use of the natural resources. The livelihood failure can contribute social insecurity, competition in access to scarce resources, unemployment, displacement and migration, discontent, emergence of conflict, collapse of governance, escalation in food prices, malnutrition and death, natural hazards *etc.* (Asanga (2001) and Kvitashvili (2005)).

The natural environment offers people a wide range of economically valuable assets and irreplaceable services necessary for life. Forests are one such complex and multipurpose asset that provides various resources that enable various livelihoods. (FAO 2001; Zewdie 2002). They are a critical part of the normal resource base and are fit for giving a wide range of natural, financial, social and cultural services that upgrades the capacities, resources and exercises expected for a method for living. Forests give a variety of advantages to people and society. Alongside important ecological services, it has been succeedingly acknowledged that the forests harbor a critical level of worldwide populace for their livelihoods. The World Bank Report, 2002 shows that about one-quarter of the world's population (1.6 billion) depend to varying degrees on forests for their livelihoods. Among them, 60 million indigenous people are almost wholly dependent on forests and some 350 million people who live in or adjacent to forests depend on them to a high degree for subsistence and income. In India, some 68 million souls, belonging to 227 different ethnic groups, and comprising of 573 tribal communities live within or near forests depending for livelihoods on varying degree (Rai and Nath 2003; Kumar and Saxena 2002). These means that, forest peripheries are mostly inhabited by tribal societies and worlds' most critical and poverty-stricken populations and that the forest resources are very crucial for the sustenance of livelihoods of these communities.

Studies on household's dependence on forests have distinguished three different functions the forests provide in rural livelihoods (Angelsen and Wunder 2003; Cavendish 2003 and Vedeld et al. 2007). They are identified as-

1. Safety-net Functions: Forest products are used to overcome unexpected income shortfalls or cash needs.
2. Support of Current Consumption: Forest products are important to maintain the current level of consumption and prevent the household from falling into (deeper) poverty.

3. A Pathway out of Poverty: Forest products provide a way to increase household income sustainably either through a ‘stepping-out’ strategy (accumulation of capital to move into other activities) or a ‘stepping-up’ strategy (intensification and specialization in existing activities).

During distress when food is scarce and there is no cash to purchase essential products from commercial sources, forests form a “safety net” allowing the rural poor to survive through hardships and recurrent “hungry seasons” after families have finished the previous years’ crops, and new crops are yet to come. The indigenous community is dependent on sanctuary resources in a variety of ways. These were in terms of fruits, nuts, leaves, flowers, seeds, gum, honey, medicines, fuel wood, fodder, logs of wood\ timber, meat, animal skins, grass, barks of trees for ropes, space for grazing and others (ibid). Looking towards the parliamentary initiatives on tribal affairs; even after seventy-two years of independence, tribal communities are living in sub-human conditions. In the name of development, the giant corporates are exploiting the natural resources, earlier the resources which were at the doorstep of tribals.

The main intention of this study was to have an in-depth enquiry into the livelihood conditions of the inhabitants of the fringe villages of the Pilibhit Tiger Reserve.

Research Design- Exploratory research design will be used in the study.

Universe: The study will focus on the fringe villages adjacent to Pilibhit Tiger Reserve. The proposed study will cover households from the fringe villages of Pilibhit Tiger Reserve.

Sampling and sample size: Sampling used would be multi stage proportionate sampling. The fringe villages are divided into 4 ranges. One village from each range would be selected in the sample based on the population obtained from census data. Of the total population of the village, proportion of 10% of the population will be taken as sample.

S.No	Village Name	Households	Sample Households
1	Mahof	384	38
2	Nadaha	424	42
3	Naujliya Naktah	743	74
4	Navdiya Tanda Chatrapti	44	04
Total		3070	158

Tools of data collection-The present study adopted mixed approach (qualitative as well as quantitative methods) to explore the objectives of the study.

Primary data: Primary data will be collected through structured interview schedule from respondents. The interview schedule will be based on the objectives of the study and accordingly assess the various aspects of the respondents.

Secondary data: Secondary data is existing information that has been, or will be, collected by others for another purpose. This may include reports from other organizations, data collected from previous studies. The critical distinction between primary and secondary data is that primary data is collected specifically for the baseline study. Secondary data have been, or will be, collected for another original purpose.

Results

Table 1: Occupation profile of the respondents

Occupation	Mahof	Nadaha	Naujliya Naktah	Navdiya Tanda Chatrapti	Overall
Farming	52%	66%	59%	59%	59%
Day labour	1%	6%	4%	4%	4%

Pvt. Service; Govt. Service	6%	4%	8%	6%	6%
Livestock rearing	30%	20%	25%	25%	25%
Appointed by Forest dept.	11%	4%	4%	6%	6%

Occupation profile of the household population states that majority of population that is 59% is into farming followed by 25% of population which is into livestock rearing. However very small proportion of the population that is 4 to 6% is into day labor private or government service or are appointed by Forest department. Therefore, it can be stated that majority of the household population is into occupation of farming.

Table 2: Annual income of the household population

Annual income of the household	Mahof	Nadaha	Naujliya Naktah	Navdiya Tanda Chatrapti	Overall
less than 10,000	10%	12%	7%	9%	10%
10001-20000	35%	39%	40%	35%	37%
20001-30000	29%	25%	29%	30%	28%
30001-40000	24%	21%	22%	22%	22%
More than 40000	2%	3%	2%	4%	3%

The table above shows the distribution of household population on the basis of their annual income. It can be established from the table that 37% of the population has their annual income ranging between 100001 to 20000 and 28% of the population has their annual income in between 20000 to 30000. Moreover 22% of the population has their income ranging between 300001 to 40000. It can be further established that 8% percent of the population has annual income less than 10000 and a very low proportion of the population that is 3% has their annual income more than 40000. Therefore, it can be said that majority of population has their annual income from 10000 to 30000.

Table 3: Facilities available at the village

Facilities village	at	Mahof	Nadaha	Naujliya Naktah	Navdiya Tanda Chatrapti	Overall
Health Facility		95%	20%	73%	67%	64%
Safe Drinking Water		92%	88%	80%	89%	87%
Pucca Road		10%	15%	10%	69%	26%
Transportations		17%	75%	25%	77%	49%
Cleanliness and Sanitation		11%	15%	10%	20%	14%

When inquired about the facilities available at the village 87% of the response a firm that they get safe drinking water whereas 64% of the respondents are formed that there is health facility present in their village. Moreover 49% of the respondents affirmed that transportation facility was available in their village followed by 26% of respondents stated that there was pakka road available in their village. However only 14% of the respondents a affirmed that the cleanliness

and sanitation facilities are available at the village which indicates that there is no proper drainage system or garbage disposal system. In the context of health facility, in the village Nadaha only 20% of the household at affirmed about the health facility in the village. Thus, it can be concluded that health facility, save drinking water and pakka road etc. are present in the village but cleanliness and sanitation facilities are still lacking in the villages.

Table 4: Type of land holding owned

Type of Land Holding	Mahof	Nadaha	Naujliya Naktah	Navdiya Tanda Chatrapti	Overall
Irrigated	1.9%	3.7%	3.7%	0.0%	2%
Non-irrigated	18.5%	40.7%	16.7%	5.6%	21%

When inquired about the type of land holding owned by the household population it was found that only 2% of the household population had irrigated land holding whereas the remaining population had non irrigated land holding.

Table 5: Have their own land

Own Land	Mahof	Nadaha	Naujliya Naktah	Navdiya Tanda Chatrapti	Overall
Yes	14%	29%	29%	32%	26%
No	86%	71%	71%	68%	74%

The above table shows the proportion of population who have their own land. 74% of the respondents stated that they do not on their own land and only 26% of the respondents a formed about having own land. Therefore, majority of population do not have own land so they have to depend on other sources of income generation.

Table 6: Problems associated with agriculture

Problems with Agriculture	Mahof	Nadaha	Naujliya Naktah	Navdiya Tanda Chatrapti	Overall
Disease / Insects	39%	45%	57%	49%	48%
Too Much / Too Little Rain	53%	60%	47%	51%	53%
Low Yield	25%	32%	29%	22%	27%
Crop Raiding by Wild Animals	49%	29%	33%	41%	38%
Insufficient Land	4%	6%	3%	5%	5%

From the above table the problems associated with agriculture can be studied. It is observed that too much for two little rain was confirmed by 53% of the population where as 48% of the population stated that disease or insects are the problems faced during agriculture followed by 38% of the population which stated that crop reading by wild animals is the problem faced by them during agriculture. Around 27% of the household populations among that low yield of produce is one of the problems associated with agriculture. Therefore, irregular rain disease and crop riding by wild animals are the major problems associated with agriculture as identified in the table above.

Table 7: Household ever taken loan

Taken loan	Mahof	Nadaha	Naujliya Naktah	Navdiya Tanda Chatrapti	Overall

Yes	10%	12%	8%	5%	9%
No	90%	88%	92%	95%	91%

The table above shows the proportion of households who have taken loan for various reasons. It can be established from the table above that only 9% of the households have taken loan in the past 2 years whereas remaining 91% of the population has not taken or applied for loan. Thus, it can be stated that lower number of household population is applying for loan and when inquired further it was stated that they are not aware of the loaning process.

Table 8: Purpose for loan

Purpose of Loan	Mahof	Nadaha	Naujliya Naktah	Navdiya Tanda Chatrapti	Overall
Land/Farm Improvement	78%	59%	50%	0%	47%
Irrigation Facilities (Dug Well/Bore Well, Farm Pond)	52%	59%	67%	0%	45%
Petty Trade/ Business	0%	0%	34%	0%	9%
Medical Expenses	0%	20%	0%	0%	5%
Education	4%	9%	8%	0%	5%
Marriage	2%	1%	3%	2%	2%
House Construction/Purchase/Repair	0%	20%	17%	0%	9%
Purchase of Land	5%	4%	2%	3%	4%
Purchase of Jewelry/Durable Goods	1%	2%	1%	2%	2%
To Buy Animals	3%	2%	3%	2%	3%
Death Related Expenses	2%	1%	3%	3%	2%

From the table above it can be studied the different purposes for which the forest villagers apply for loan. 47% of the household population stated that their purpose for taking loan is land or farm improvement followed by 45% of population which stated that they took loan for developing irrigation facilities. Moreover 9% of the respondents stated that they took loan for house construction or purchase and repair. The other purposes for taking loan were medical expenses 5%, education 5%, marriage 2%, buy animals 2% etc.

Table 9: Whether willing to migrate to other place

Willingness to Migrate	Mahof	Nadaha	Naujliya Naktah	Overall
Yes	71%	75%	80%	75%

No	29%	25%	20%	25%
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The table above depicts the status of migration of the population of the village. When inquired about whether the respondents migrate or not, around 75% of the respondents stated that they do migrate from village where as 25% of the respondents did not migrate from village. Therefore, it can be said that migration can be seen in high frequency among forest villagers.

Table 10: Reason for migration

Reason for Migration	Mahof	Nadaha	Naujliya Naktah	Overall
Higher Wage	91%	100%	30%	74%
Lack of Employment	82%	45%	53%	60%
Safety Threats	18%	18%	20%	19%
Poverty	39%	27%	33%	33%
Livelihood Issues	45%	82%	60%	62%

The respondents were further enquired about their reason for migration. Out of the respondents those who affirmed that they migrate, 74% of the respondents migrate in search of higher wage where as 60% of the respondents migrate due to lack of employment in their current place of residence. Further 62% of respondents stated that they migrate due to livelihood issues and 33% of the respondents migrate from one place to another in order to cope up with the poverty. Therefore, higher age lack of employment and lively good issues are some of the common reasons for migration of forest villagers.

Conclusion

The findings of the present study led to conclude that the tribal communities are in underprivileged position in all respects as reflected by their low socio-personal and economic status, acute poverty, poor employment opportunities leading to migration, insufficient communication and extension facilities, low infrastructure, poor education and health care facilities. The possession of livelihood assets in terms of physical, natural, financial, human and social capitals is unsatisfactory resulting in vulnerable overall livelihood assets status among majority of the households in the study site. Livelihood diversification using existing resources is thus needed as important strategy of poverty reduction and socioeconomic upliftment of backward tribal people in the area.

In order to make the forest based tribal livelihoods stronger, secured and sustainable, specific livelihood interventions are required. Moreover, the overall livelihood assets status consisted of physical, natural, financial, human and social capitals were found to be vulnerable, there is an urgent need to create sustainable livelihoods for the tribal people in the area. Thus, development of specific livelihood strategies using existing resources is needed to achieve sustainable livelihoods.

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